

ERRORS IN ARITHMETIC COMPUTATION OF SIXTH STANDARD PUPILS OF BANTWAL TALUK

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ABSTRACT

The present study is titled as “Errors in arithmetic computation of sixth standard pupils of Bantwal taluk”. The central goal of education is not just leading to read and write but to develop the abilities to think and reason. Reasoning is the heart of education. This is more explicit in the education of Science and Mathematics than other fields. In the report of the Education Commission (1964-66) it is recommended that Sciences and Mathematics should be taught on the compulsory basis to all pupils as a part of general education during the first ten years of schooling.

A difficulty in learning Mathematics is not generally a number based one but can be concept based or competency based. Some children learn to solve problems by mastery of steps in a procedure with a fixed order, and errors appear when the problem is presented in a different format or when the test is made up of a variety of problems. Survey method is used to select a sample of 600 students of sixth standard studying in 13 Kannada medium higher primary schools. A Diagnostic test is developed to assess the conceptual errors encountered in mathematical operations in selected areas of arithmetic. . The results of the statistical analyses reveal that a) Distribution of error scores in arithmetic computation for the total sample showed that pupils make maximum number of errors in division. b) Distribution of error scores based on gender showed that the total error scores of boys than that of girls. c) Distribution of error scores based on type of management of schools showed that the total error scores of government school pupils are higher than that of aided school pupils.

This reveals that there are deficiencies in the teaching of arithmetic. To enhance teachers’ use of student’s experiences, teacher education will need to focus on encouraging a variety of ways of teacher-student interaction during which students’ mathematical ideas should be considered exhaustively.

Keywords: Errors, arithmetic, computation, diagnostic test.

Introduction

The present system of education geared to produce, citizens who can deal with the words, concepts and mathematical or scientific symbols which are necessary for success in a technological society. In classroom, where traditional teaching is followed, pupils are passive listeners and mathematics is learned with tears. Pupils fail to inquire into the subject and solve problems themselves.

Need for the study

We have seen that mathematics has been as important part of the school curriculum ever because it gives the strong foundation to the education. Mathematics should be visualized as the vehicle to train a child to think, reason, analyse and articulate logically. Considering its role in the daily life of human beings arithmetic which is a branch of mathematics has special importance. Today, arithmetic is taught with special emphasis on its practical uses in life considering its importance gaining proficiency in arithmetic specially on process of operations like addition, subtraction, multiplication and division is a must. But it is fact that many go wrong or make mistakes even while doing simple calculations or computations. For this we have to go to the primary school level, where the children learn the basis of arithmetic computations.

Pupils disability in arithmetic computation is a black mark to our educational system. A large number of studies are done on the concepts related to nature of arithmetic operations and along with effective and remedial teaching. But such studies are very few in our country. Hence there is a need to study what types of errors are committed by the pupils in arithmetic especially at the primary level.

Objectives of the study

1. To find the distribution of errors of computation in selected areas of arithmetic of sixth standard pupils of Bantwal taluk based on a) Gender, b) Type of management of schools

Methodology used

The present study is a descriptive study whose purpose was to survey the ‘errors in arithmetic computation of sixth standard pupils of Bantwal taluk’. The errors in arithmetic computation involved the process of operations namely addition, subtraction, multiplication and division.

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Research method used

Phase one a) Selection of the variables involved in the study b) Construction and validation of the diagnostic tool to measure the selected variable
Phase two a) Selection of the sample involved in the study b) Collection of the data using the prepared tool
Phase three a) Scoring the collected data using appropriate scoring procedure b) Analysis of the data using suitable statistical procedure

Variables of the study

In order to meet the objectives of the study the investigator selected the only variable ‘**error in arithmetic computation**’.

Sample of the study

The sample of the study involved six hundred students studying in sixth standard of different schools of Kannada medium in bantwal taluk. Eleven schools which were selected randomly from a list of one hundred seventy schools. Five of these schools were government schools and six were aided schools.

Tools used in the study

To measure the only variable of the study “error in arithmetic computation’ in selected areas, the investigator constructed a test “a diagnostic test to detect the errors in arithmetic computation in mathematics”. The areas selected for arithmetic computations were fraction, decimal and percentages.

Analysis and interpretation of the study

The objective of the study was to find the distribution of error scores in arithmetic computation of the sixth standard pupils of Bantwal Taluk in selected areas based on i) gender and ii) type of management of schools. This objective was analysed in three stages

- A. Distribution of error scores in arithmetic computation for the total sample
- B. Distribution of error scores based on Gender
- C. Distribution of error scores based on types of management of schools

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A. Distribution of error scores in arithmetic computation for the total sample

SAMPLE	PROCESS OF OPERATION	MEAN ERROR SCORES (%)
600	Addition	66.12
	Subtraction	74.27
	Multiplication	71.95
	Division	90.73
	Total	75.4

From the table it is evident that error scores in the process of division are the highest. This may be due to lack of negligence towards division, not knowing the multiplication tables, cancellation of common numbers and so on. Teacher may not efficient enough to teach the process of division according to the difficulties of the pupils. Teachers may not give more drill work to the pupils in division problems because it takes more time to solve the problem. If more drill work is given then errors can be minimized.

Total error score is very high. This indicates that the teachers need to concentrate on error scores along with achievement scores and remedial measures need to be taken for improving mathematics education. Since the studies were less to support the findings of the present study, it was not possible to arrive at any generalization.

B. Distribution of error scores based on Gender

GENDER	SAMPLE	PROCESS OF OPERATION	MEAN ERROR SCORES (%)	SD
BOYS	300	Addition	70.86	26.60
		Subtraction	76.78	25.82
		Multiplication	75.10	24.39
		Division	92.35	18.96
		Total	78.12	20.2
GIRLS	300	Addition	62.02	28.59
		Subtraction	71.78	27.09
		Multiplication	68.84	27.20
		Division	89.20	20.47
		Total	72.71	21.50

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From the table, it is evident that Boys error scores are higher than those of girls. Since the investigator was not able to find more related finding the present study could not be generalized.

C. Distribution of error scores based on types of management of schools

GENDER	SAMPLE	PROCES S OF OPERATI ON	MEAN ERRO R SCOR ES (%)	SD
GOVERNMENT	300	Addition	72.43	26.60
		Subtractio n	75.53	25.82
		Multiplicat ion	75.72	24.39
		Division	94.32	18.96
		Total	78.32	20.2
AIDEDD	300	Addition	60.94	26.61
		Subtractio n	70.21	24.17
		Multiplicat ion	68.85	24.82
		Division	87.78	22.44
		Total	71.64	21.00

From the table, it is evident that the government schools make more errors than that of aided schools in the process of operation addition, subtraction, multiplication and division.

This may be due to the carelessness, due to carrying over confidence of the pupils in solving problems. Since the investigator was not able to find more related finding the present study could not be generalized.

Major findings of the study

1. Distribution of error scores in arithmetic computation for the total sample showed that pupils make maximum number of errors in division
2. Distribution of error scores in based on gender showed that the total error scores of boys are higher than that of girls.
3. Distribution of error scores in based on types of schools showed that the total error scores of Government school pupils are higher than that of aided school pupils.

Educational implications of the study

1. It helps the school teachers to identify the common errors in arithmetic computation by the pupils in the process of operation
2. The study provides suitable guidelines to the teachers as to how to analyze the answers of the student and thus help to providing remedial teaching.
3. Special attention could be given to the students of low achievement. Special programs and other supplementary materials should be provided to improve their achievement.
4. Pupils should be given proper training to i) read problems carefully and comprehend the problems, ii) find out the appropriate steps in solving the problem.

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